

The Oil from the Seeds of *Putranjiva Roxburghii*, Wall.

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Putranjiva Roxburghii, Wall (N. O. *Euphorbiaceæ*; Vernacular—*Jiputa* or *Putranjiva*) is a moderate-sized evergreen tree with pendant branches, met wild and cultivated, throughout tropical India, from the lower Himalayas in Kumaon, eastwards and southwards, to Pegu and Ceylon. The leaves and stones of the fruit are officinal in certain parts of India and are given in decoction in colds and fevers. The seeds yield a pale yellow oil, which on standing deposits a small amount of solid matter and turns deeper in colour. "The stones of the fruit are strung together to form rosaries and hung round the necks of children to keep them in good health," hence the Sanskrit and the Vernacular names which signify 'the life of the child.' Hooper (Kirtikar and Basu, 'Indian Medicinal Plants' p. 1148-49) records that in 1905 the seeds were tested in the Indian Museum and found to give 28.86% of the kernels and 42.9% of an oil in the kernels. But no data are given of the chemical examination of the oil.

Perusal of the literature shows that the oil, from putranjiva seeds, has never been examined carefully for its constituents and particularly for its active principles which are responsible for its supposed physiological effects. It was, therefore, considered a subject of interest and a chemical examination has now been made of the oil, as well as that of the pulp of the fruit, and the leaves. The oil has not shown any constituents, out of the ordinary, to which the physiological properties could be attributed. It is a glyceride of stearic, oleic, lignoceric and linoleic acids and is conspicuous by the total absence of palmitic acid. The pulp of the fruit, however, has been found to contain a large proportion of mannitol, a small quantity of a saponin glucoside, and a small quantity of an unidentified alkaloid.

Examination of the 'unsaponifiable matter' has shown it to contain sitosterol, which is unlikely to give the oil its therapeutic value. A small amount of a waxy matter, presumably a hydrocarbon of a high molecular weight, has also been separated from the unsaponifiable matter but its precise nature has not yet been identified. Tests for the presence of vitamins have also been made, both in the

oil and its unsaponifiable matter, and were found to be negative. From this it is concluded that the physiological activity of putranjiva, if at all there is any, is in all likelihood due to the glucoside and the alkaloid, a small quantity of which is also present in the stones of the fruit.

The putranjiva seeds used in this investigation were collected from trees in the Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun.

Stones of the ripe fruit were collected, washed, dried and the kernels separated. The nuts contained 46 per cent. of kernels which in turn yielded 25% of the oil soluble in ether, the yield of crude oil was thus about 12% of the whole nut. The oil obtained by cold expression was of light pale yellow colour and clear in nature, but on standing for some weeks it deposited a fine curdy precipitate and also its colour deepened to an orange shade. A sample of the oil which was extracted in 1925 had turned deep orange in colour and its physical constants are noted below for purposes of comparison.

General Characteristics of the Oil.

	1930 oil.	1925 oil.
Consistency	Thin, clear	Thick, turbid due to sediment.
Colour	Pale yellow	Deep orange
Specific gravity at 30°/30°	0.9108	0.9233
Refractive index at 25°	1.4615	1.4623
Saponification value	189.9	198.50
Iodine value (Hanus)	93.8	79.49
Acetyl value	9.5	43.30
Hehner value	95.4	96.20
Unsaponifiable matter	0.75%	0.73%
Acid value	0.9	11.13

Composition of the Fatty Acids of Putranjiva Oil.

The fatty acids present in the kernels have been quantitatively investigated according to the customary methods of preliminary separation by the lead salt—alcohol method (Twitchell, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806) into groups consisting respectively of mainly saturated and of mainly unsaturated acids, followed by conversion of each groups into methyl esters and systematic fractionation of the latter under vacuum. The results obtained are tabulated below. The liquid acids were found to consist chiefly of oleic (80%) and the linoleic (20%), while the solid acids consisted of stearic and

lignoceric. No attempt has been made to calculate the percentages of the solid acids as the nature of the intermediate products is not definitely known.

Chemical Constants of the Mixed Fatty Acids.

Mean molecular weight	...	...	292.5
Iodine value (Hanus)	...	...	101.9
Saturated acids (Twitchell's method)	...	...	21.4 per cent.
Unsaturated acids	...	...	77.6 per cent.

The crude fatty acids (389 g.) from 457 g. of the oil were treated with a slight excess of sodium hydroxide and the resultant soap was incorporated with filter paper pulp. The mass was dried, powdered and extracted with ether in a Soxhlet and the extract examined for unsaponifiable matter as described below.

Unsaturated Acids.

Methyl esters of the fatty acids were prepared in the usual manner (refluxing the acids with methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid) and 85 g. of these were fractionated at 2 mm.

Fraction.	B.p.	Weight.	M.W. of the acids.	Iodine value.
L ₁	50°–155°	1.23 g.	184.4	59.7
L ₂	155°–165°	1.10	211.9	75.6
L ₃	165°–170°	2.63	237.5	83.9
L ₄	170°–175°	3.13	239.7	86.7
L ₅	175°–176°	31.44	260.6	96.4
L ₆	176°–177°	8.04	260.1	98.9
L ₇	177°–180°	2.78	255.0	96.5
L ₈	180°–183°	6.15	265.2	100.6
L ₉	183°–185°	12.69	274.3	100.1
L ₁₀	185°–195°	3.43	246.0	88.9
L ₁₁	195°–210°	1.50	233.0	83.1
L ₁₂	Residue	9.78		
Loss in distillation		1.10		
Total		85.00 g.		

Of the above esters fractions L₅, L₆, L₇, L₈, and L₉ were mixed together and separately hydrolysed for further examination, the other fractions were left alone, being too small in amounts. The resulting soaps were oxidised with potassium permanganate in dilute cold solution and the hydroxy-acids obtained on neutralising the

mixture with sulphur dioxide were successively extracted with petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°) to remove the unoxidised acids and the decomposition products. The residue, on extraction with ether, gave a product which on crystallisation from alcohol yielded an acid of M.W. 323 and m.p. 130-31°. These properties correspond very closely with those of dihydroxystearic acid. The residue, on further crystallisation, gave products melting over a wide range of temperature (155°-180°) but having molecular weight of the order of 348. This is not considered strange as many investigators (Power and Barrowcliff, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 899; Power and Moore, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1103; Power and Salway, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 32, 350; Tummin Katti and Puntambekar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 223) have found that acids agreeing in composition and character with tetrahydroxystearic acid possessed melting points varying from 156° to 173° and it is probable, therefore, that these compounds represent isomeric acids of the formula $C_{18}H_{36}O_6$. No hexahydroxystearic acid was found in the aqueous portion of the oxidised sodium soaps of the liquid acids.

A portion of the liquid acids on bromination (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology & Analysis of Oils, Fats & Waxes," Vol. I, 6th edition, p. 585) gave no hexabromides. It, however, yielded a pale yellow product melting at 113-14° which was identified as tetrabromostearic acid by its mixed melting point with an authentic sample of tetrabromostearic acid.

The examination of the products of oxidation and bromination of the liquid acids, therefore, indicates in it the presence of oleic and linoleic acids, the former being 80% and the latter 20% of the liquid acids.

Saturated Acids.

The methyl esters (62 g.) of these acids on fractional distillation under a pressure of 2 mm. gave the following fractions:

Fraction.	B. p.	Weight.	M. W. of the acids.
S ₁	Up to 162°	1.04 g.	247.0
S ₂	162°-167°	4.24	257.4
S ₃	167°-171°	2.71	260.3
S ₄	171°-173°	23.93	264.4
S ₅	173°-176°	6.31	267.3
S ₆	176°-177°	5.30	272.9
S ₇	177°-179°	5.94	280.2
S ₈	179°-181°	3.06	282.7
S ₉	181°-185°	2.58	290.1
S ₁₀	185°-200°	3.34	312.4
S ₁₁	Above 200°	3.00	
	Loss in distillation	0.55	
		62.00 g.	

The acids liberated from each of the fractions were subjected to fractional crystallisation to identify the individual acids.

Fraction S₁.—Crystallisation from dilute alcohol gave a product of m.p. 67-68° and M. W. 283. It was identified as stearic acid on taking a mixed melting point with an authentic sample.

Fraction S₂ yielded a saturated acid of m.p. 68-69° (unchanged when mixed with stearic acid) and M.W. 315. The filtrate from the above yielded a product, m.p. 56-57° and M.W. 274. The residue had a M.W. of 315.

Fraction S₃.—After several crystallisations it yielded a product, m.p. 60-63° and M.W. 284 ; mixed m.p. with pure stearic acid was slightly higher, consequently appeared to be impure stearic acid. The residue from the filtrate, on concentration and crystallisation gave a M.W. 238.

Fraction S₄ gave an acid melting at 68-69° (unchanged when mixed with stearic acid). The mother-liquor on further concentrations gave a material melting at 54° and M.W. 292·6. The final residue had M.W. 376.

Fraction S₅.—On crystallisation from alcohol the acid melted at 68-69° and had M.W. 288 ; identified as stearic acid. The residue on concentration and crystallisation gave a substance of M.W. 378.

Fraction S₆ gave an acid m. p. 67·5-68·5° and M. W. 286 ; identified as stearic acid. The filtrate gave two products of M.W.'s. 323 and 346 respectively.

Fraction S₇ gave a product melting at 68-69° (not depressed when mixed with pure stearic acid). From the filtrate two products were obtained having M.W.'s. 354 and 396 respectively.

Fraction S₈.—From this fraction stearic acid was isolated and identified as above. The filtrate gave products having M. W.'s. 313 and 339 respectively.

Fraction S₉.—No definite acid could be isolated from this fraction. The crystalline product obtained had a m.p. 62-63·5° and M.W. 296·5, indicating it to be impure stearic acid. On crystallisation of the filtrates a residue of M.W. 337 was obtained.

Fraction S₁₀ gave no definite acid. The product after several crystallisations from alcohol melted at 61-63° and M.W. 304·8. The filtrate on further concentrations and crystallisation yielded products of M.W. 396 and 318.

Fraction S₁₁ gave an acid of m.p. 77·5-78·5° and M.W. 370. Its mixed melting point with lignoceric acid remained unaltered.

The filtrate residue consisted mainly of the colouring matters and decomposition products.

The residues from the filtrate of the Fractions S₂—S₁₁ were combined together and crystallised from alcohol, when a colourless crystalline product of m.p. 59-61° and M.W. 284 was obtained, and it appeared to be impure stearic acid. The filtrate on further concentration and crystallisation gave an acid of M.W. 348.5. The residue obtained had a M.W. 454 and m.p. below 55°. The acids (M.W. 348.5 and 454), on further examination were found to be mixtures of esters and free acids both of which on hydrolysis yielded an acid of M.W. 282, which presumably is stearic acid.

Unsaponifiable Matter.

The unsaponifiable matter after several crystallisations from rectified spirit gave a white crystalline product m.p. 143-145° and gave all the characteristic tests of phytosterol. The acetyl derivative after crystallisation melted at 129-130°. This phytosterol has been identified as sitosterol.

A small amount of a waxy material presumably a hydrocarbon of high molecular weight, insoluble in concentrated sulphuric acid was also obtained from the unsaponifiable matter but the amount was too small for identification purposes.

Summary.

The oil from the seeds of *Putranjiva Roxburghii* has been found to contain the glycerides of stearic, lignoceric, oleic and linoleic acids together with sitosterol melting at 143-145°. The presence of palmitic acid has not been detected.